

Synergistic effects of high-pressure processing and interface engineering in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ photovoltaic devices

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ABSTRACT

We report an innovative high-pressure post-deposition annealing for co-evaporated Sb_2Se_3 absorber layers, demonstrating for its effectiveness for enhancing the crystallographic texture along the [00 1] direction. This process promotes growth parallel to the *c*-axis, favoring carrier transport and yielding highly crystalline films with crystallite sizes exceeding 100 nm. Nonetheless, despite improved structural properties, photovoltaic performance remained limited by interface quality. To address this, we implemented UV- O_3 and KCN etching treatments, which significantly enhanced the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface, leading to conversion efficiencies up to 5.8 %. XPS, UPS, and contact angle measurements confirmed that these treatments selectively modify the interface without altering bulk properties. Thus, this work highlights high-pressure treatments combined with targeted interface engineering as a promising strategy for optimizing Sb_2Se_3 -based thin-film solar cells.

1. Introduction

The field of photovoltaic technologies is experiencing a significant transformation as it expands into emerging, non-traditional niche markets. This evolution has created an increasing need for developing new materials and devices specifically tailored to meet the demands of these innovative applications. Among the emerging technologies, Van der Waals (VdW) semiconductors have garnered significant attention due to their rapid development and anisotropic features, including enhanced carrier transport along certain crystallographic directions. [1,2] In general, a material can be considered to exhibit VdW characteristics when the electronegativity difference between its anion and cation is lower than 1.5. [3] However, it is important to stress that this is a phenomenological rule based on empirical evidence alone. Notably, a variety of VdW materials have been identified so far, including metal

chalcogenides like $\text{Sb}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$, $\text{Bi}_2(\text{S,Se})_3$, GeSe_2 and SnSe ; halides, such as BiI_3 and SbI_3 ; and mixed chalcogenides, including SbSeI , SbSI , BiSI , and BiSeI [4–10]. These compounds are characterized by their remarkable structural and compositional versatility, predominantly exhibiting a low-dimensional structure. [11] This distinctive feature is crucial for their potential implementation into photovoltaic applications, as the optoelectronic properties can vary significantly along in-plane or out-of-plane directions. Such anisotropic behavior enables enhanced control over charge transport properties, light absorption, and exciton dynamics, which are essential for optimizing device performance in the next-generation solar energy technologies.

In particular, Sb_2Se_3 has emerged as a prominent member of the growing family of low-dimensional semiconductors, attracting considerable attention over the past decade. Notably, photovoltaic devices based on Sb_2Se_3 have achieved power conversion efficiencies exceeding

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10 % within a relatively short timeframe.[12] This rapid progress is largely attributed to the material's favorable intrinsic properties, including bandgap in the optimal range for solar energy harvesting (1.1–1.3 eV), and a high absorption coefficient (up to 10^5 cm^{-1}). Structurally, Sb_2Se_3 exhibits a characteristic quasi-1D structure, consisting of covalently bonded $(\text{Sb}_4\text{Se}_6)_n$ ribbons oriented along a single crystallographic direction (typically the [00 1] axis). Likewise, these ribbons are weakly held together by non-directional Van der Waals forces in the remaining spatial directions, resulting in that the highly anisotropic charge transport is enhanced along the covalently-bonded chains. Despite these advantages, challenges remain regarding charge carrier lifetime and overall mobility, which still require significant improvement. Advances in thin-film deposition techniques and thermal treatments have played a crucial role in gradually enhancing these characteristics, advancing towards achieving the material's full potential. Nevertheless, critical issues such as effective defect passivation and precise control over crystalline orientation remain unresolved and are key to unlocking further performance improvements.[13–16].

Precise control over the crystalline orientation is widely recognized as a critical factor in fully unlocking the potential of Sb_2Se_3 , [17] as well as in other quasi-1D chalcogenides such as GeSe_2 and Sb_2S_3 . [18–20] Indeed, various studies have demonstrated that an optimized crystalline orientation directly enhances their optoelectronic properties and overall device performance. To address this issue, a broad range of strategies have been developed in order to tailor the crystallographic texture of chalcogenide films, however, each approach was carefully adapted to suit the particular fabrication technique employed.[21] Among these strategies, fine-tuning the growth conditions has shown promising results in promoting favorable crystalline orientation,[17,22] as well as the implementation of interface engineering to enable a more ordered crystallization,[12] and the strategic use of lattice-matched substrates to guide epitaxial alignment.[23,24] Furthermore, post-deposition treatments and the incorporation of seeding layers have been successfully employed to control nucleation and guide the crystal growth, ensuring the formation of films with a well-defined texture.[25–29] Thus, this comprehensive set of techniques provides the ideal framework for controlling the structural and crystallographic properties of quasi-1D chalcogenides, ultimately resulting in significant improvements in charge transport and optoelectronic performance. Thus, the effect of crystallographic orientation on device performance has been consistently reported, underscoring the essential impact of texture engineering on the advancement of optoelectronic device efficiency.

In this work, we explore a modified approach to the synthesis of Sb_2Se_3 absorber layers for photovoltaic applications, employing a high-pressure thermal treatment aimed at enhancing the material's structural properties by operating at pressures exceeding 1 atm. While reactive annealing is a well-established physical vapor deposition technique widely used for chalcogenide synthesis, it is typically performed under vacuum or atmospheric pressure conditions.[30–33] To the best of our knowledge, this study represents the first report of Sb_2Se_3 thin films manufactured through a selenization process conducted at pressures up to 20 atm. This innovative technique provides a new strategy for selectively controlling the crystallographic texture of Sb_2Se_3 , enabling a deeper understanding of the interplay between synthesis conditions, applied pressure, and texture development. Specifically, we show that applying high pressure during the process significantly enhances the texture coefficient along the [00 1] crystallographic direction. Also, this study offers valuable insights into the critical role that preferential orientation plays in determining the electrical and optoelectronic properties, as well as the overall performance of Sb_2Se_3 -based devices. To illustrate the impact of our methodology on the device performance, we fabricated solar cells using the following substrate configuration: $\text{Mo/Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}/\text{i-ZnO}/\text{ITO}$. Extensive characterization was carried out, including X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS), providing detailed compositional profiling and band structure analysis. As a result of this optimization

process, we achieved a device efficiency approaching 6 %, representing a significant improvement compared to reference devices fabricated without the high-pressure treatment. This advancement highlights the potential of our approach to contribute meaningfully to the development of Sb_2Se_3 thin-film photovoltaics.

2. Experimental methodology

2.1. Synthesis of Sb_2Se_3 samples by a high-pressure PVD method

Sb_2Se_3 was deposited on commercial glass/Mo substrates by co-evaporation from elemental sources of Sb (Sigma-Aldrich, 100 mesh, 99.5 %) and Se (Thermo-Scientific, 200 mesh, 99.999 %), which were heated at 550 °C and 230 °C respectively, while the substrate was kept at a constant temperature of 270 °C. For a thickness of 600 nm, the deposition was carried out for 40 min with a stable base vacuum of 10^{-7} mbar. Importantly, after this process, a strictly stoichiometric Sb_2Se_3 film is obtained ($\text{Se/Sb} = 0.5$). However, previous research has demonstrated that the optoelectronic performance and p-type doping can be further enhanced under Se-rich conditions.[3,34] Hence, all the samples are subsequently subjected to a post-deposition thermal treatment under reactive Se atmosphere, in a tubular furnace. This process aims to obtain Se-richer films (64–65 at.% Se, 35–36 % at.Sb), while also improving the crystalline quality and crystallographic texture of polycrystalline Sb_2Se_3 samples. See Fig. 1 for an illustrative schematics of the whole process.

The post-deposition annealing treatment is carried out in a steel tubular furnace capable of reaching processing temperatures up to 600 °C, and operating under high pressure conditions. The $\text{Mo/Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ precursor was placed in a borosilicate Petri dish along with 5 mg of selenium powder. The Petri dish was then introduced into the thermally stable region of the furnace, which was hermetically sealed, and the internal pressure was increased by inletting argon (Ar) into the tube. All annealing processes were conducted at temperatures ranging from 300 °C to 500 °C. Under these conditions, the pressure during the treatment varied between 0.3 MPa and 2.0 MPa, depending on the starting pressure and processing temperature. Throughout the remainder of this work, all reported pressure values refer to the final pressure, i.e., the pressure maintained during the annealing process, rather than the initial Ar pressure set at the beginning of the heating ramp.

In addition to the $\text{Mo/Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ samples, solar cells have been fabricated with the following substrate architecture: $\text{glass/Mo/Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}/\text{ZnO}/\text{ITO}$. 50 nm of CdS (acting as electron transport layer) were deposited by chemical bath deposition (CBD), using the procedure reported elsewhere.[13,35] Finally, a transparent conductive oxide layer based on ZnO + ITO (In-doped SnO_2) was deposited by DC-pulsed magnetron sputtering (Alliance Concept CT100).

In order to improve surface adhesion and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface quality, a number samples have been subjected to different surface treatments, including UV- O_3 cleaning and chemical etchings (based on 2 % KCN in H_2O , at room temperature).[36] Further details on the application of these treatments are discussed in the “Results and discussion” section.

2.2. Materials and device characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns have been acquired using a Bruker D8 Advance equipment in Bragg–Brentano configuration, using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54187 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Data were collected over a 2θ range of 10° to 80° , with a step size of 0.02° . The diffractograms have been analyzed using X'Pert HighScore software, supplemented by custom Python scripts for additional data processing. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs have been obtained in top-view and cross-section configuration using a Zeiss Series Auriga field-emission electron microscope, with 5 kV acceleration voltage and working distances ranging

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental methodology.

between 3 to 5 mm. RAMAN measurements have been performed with Renishaw's inVia Qontor instrument, coupled with a 2400 lines/mm visible grating and a Leica DM2700 optical microscope, using the 100x objective for confocal measurements. Samples were excited with a 532 nm laser with nominal power of 100 mW. For data acquisition, 0.5 % of the nominal power was used – 10 accumulations with 10 s of exposure time each (total exposure time: 100 s per measurement). Water contact angle (WCA) measurements were conducted with a KRÜSS Drop Shape Analyzer (DSA25E). Precisely 1 μ L of water was dropped onto the surface of the sample for every measurement. The acquired data were further examined utilizing the Sessile Drop module in the KRÜSS Advance program.

XPS and UPS experiments were performed in ESFOSCAN at CCiTUB, an equipment based on the PHI VersaProbe 4 instrument from Physical Electronics (ULVAC-PHI). XPS measurements have been done with a monochromatic focused X-ray source (Al K α line of 1486.6 eV) calibrated using the 3d5/2 line of Ag with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 0.6 eV. The analysed area was a circle of 100 μ m of diameter, sample placed at 45° with respect to the analyzer axis, and the selected resolution for the spectra was 224 eV of Pass Energy and 0.8 eV/step for the general spectra, and 27 eV of Pass Energy and 0.1 eV/step for the high-resolution spectra of the selected elements. A combination of low energy electron and ion (Ar⁺) guns (< 5 eV) was used in order to discharge samples if necessary. Measurements are referenced to the C 1 s signal, whose binding energy is equal to 284.8 eV in adventitious carbon (from atmospheric contamination). On the other hand, UPS measurements have been done using a Helium source (He I line of 21.22 eV) calibrated using an Ag sample in which the work function (WF) calculated was of 4.27 eV. The analysed area was a spot of about 1.5 mm of diameter, sample placed at 90° with respect to the analyser axis, and the selected resolution for the spectra was 1.3 eV of Pass Energy and 0.01 eV/step. Measurements were done without and with bias of about 10 eV, in order to create a well-defined onset of secondary electrons for ionization energy (IE) and work function (WF) calculation purposes. Both XPS and UPS measurements were made in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) chamber at a pressure between 5×10^{-10} and 5×10^{-9} Torr. Moreover, in order to measure beyond the Sb₂Se₃/CdS interface, into the absorber, sputtering with monoatomic Ar⁺ ion gun (at 0.5 keV) were done, with no damage appreciated in the samples when looking at the high-resolution obtained spectra. The analysis and fitting of the spectra were carried out with Multipak V. 9.0.8 program.

J-V measurements under 1-sun illumination were performed with a Pico Solar Simulator manufactured by G2V Optics, using a AM1.5G solar spectrum. Quantum efficiency measurements were performed using a Bentham PVE300 system calibrated with Si and Ge photodiodes.

3. Results

3.1. Structural and morphological study on the effect of high-pressure Sb₂Se₃ annealing

As discussed above, one of the main goals of this work is to develop innovative effective strategies to selectively control the crystallographic texture and quality of Sb₂Se₃ polycrystalline thin films. Given the complex nature of these layers, which are constituted by nanometric-sized crystallites showcasing multiple crystallographic orientations, X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements have been performed to investigate their structural features. From the diffraction patterns, full width at half maximum (FWHM) values have been extracted to estimate the grain size (which serves as an indicator of the crystalline quality), whereas the texture coefficient (TC) was calculated to evaluate the degree of preferential orientation within the polycrystalline films. It is important to note that our annealing process, conducted at moderate temperature of approximately 300 °C does not result in epitaxial layers. Therefore, we are particularly interested in identifying which families of crystallographic planes are predominantly oriented, despite the overall poly-textured nature of the samples. The TC provides a qualitative, non-absolute metric which allows comparison between different layers of different texture. It is determined by a normalization of the measured diffraction intensities with respect to those expected for randomly-oriented powder or calculated patterns. Hence, TCs larger than 1 indicate an enhanced representation of a given crystallographic plane (i.e., a preferential or preferred orientation), whereas TC values lower than 1 suggest that the corresponding planes are underrepresented in the diffraction pattern.

Additionally, the precise adjustment of the Se/Sb ratio is essential for attaining desired optoelectronic properties, optimal bandgap, and to avoid formation of undesirable secondary phases that can act as recombination centres, which are directly correlated with the solar cell's operational efficiency. Hence, the objective of our process is to exert an effective control onto the crystalline nature of the film, while simultaneously ensuring the precise regulation of the thickness and strict Se/Sb stoichiometry.[3].

Accordingly, a series of Mo/Sb₂Se₃ samples has been fabricated following the procedure described in the **Experimental methodology** section. Importantly, different applied pressures have been used, while keeping the temperature and processing time, in order to assess proficiently the impact of high-pressure annealing onto the crystalline nature of the material. Fig. 2a shows various diffractograms of the absorbers subjected to different pressure conditions – see Figs. S1 and S2 for the complete patterns of the individual samples (Fig. S2 includes a ref. untreated sample, i.e., pattern measured before annealing). By direct

Fig. 2. (a) XRD patterns of Sb₂Se₃ absorbers synthesized at four distinct pressures ranging from 0.3 to 2 MPa (final pressure). (b) Calculated texture coefficients of different Bragg reflections from the patterns above. (c) FWHM and crystallite size. (d) SEM cross-sectional images. Samples include CdS and ITO deposited on top of the absorber.

observation, it can be noted that the Bragg reflection indexed as (002) shows a higher intensity for the samples subjected to 1.7 MPa, whereas the (130), (240) and (350) peaks can only be unambiguously identified in the untreated Sb₂Se₃ and the sample processed at 0.3 MPa. Notably, the untreated film exhibits a markedly low (002) peak intensity, suggesting that thermal treatment is needed to induce crystallization and promote development of a preferred crystallographic orientation. To corroborate these observations, TCs have been calculated (Eq. (1)), see the representation of TC as a function of Miller indices in Fig. 2b. As discussed above, it is generally assumed that TC > 1 indicate an enhanced representation of a crystallographic plane with respect to the powder or calculated patterns. Likewise, if TC_{[hkl]₁} > TC_{[hkl]₂} > 1, this suggests that the [hkl]₁ crystallographic direction is more dominant than that along [hkl]₂. Finally, previous studies have suggested that in multitextured polycrystalline films, families of planes whose Miller indices satisfy $h + k + l \geq 3$ correspond to crystallographic directions that form a larger angle with respect to the substrate (i.e., more perpendicular). These orientations are generally considered more favorable for efficient charge transport in Sb₂Se₃. In particular, the [00 1] direction is completely perpendicular to the substrate and aligns with the crystal's c-axis, representing the preferred orientation that we aim to promote. On the other hand, families of planes for which $h + k \geq 3$ typically indicate lateral growth (parallel to the substrate surface), which is less desirable in our case.[16,37,38] Based on these considerations, and in the TCs shown in Fig. 2b, we can conclude that, in general, all the Sb₂Se₃ samples exhibit a certain degree of texturing which promotes the preferential perpendicular growth of the material. Notably, TC values for the (021), (101), and (002) planes are consistently greater than 1, whereas the TC_{hk0} are below 1 in all cases. Importantly, we observe that increasing the pressure leads to a general improvement in crystalline orientation, as evidenced by the clear increase in TC₀₀₂, reaching their highest levels in the samples prepared under 1.7 MPa. Also, in these samples, the TC_{hk0} values are at their lowest. However, at higher pressures (2 MPa), there is a slight decrease in TC₀₀₂, although TC₀₂₁ increases, suggesting that, overall, the dominant crystalline orientations

continue to correspond to directions that form larger angles with respect to the substrate. Therefore, we can demonstrate that synthesis processes conducted under high-pressure conditions contribute to enhancing the crystalline orientation along the c-axis direction, even if the overall texture of the samples is very complex, and there is not a single preferred orientation.

$$TC_{hkl} = \frac{I_{hkl}/I_{0,hkl}}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I_{h_i k_i l_i} / I_{0, h_i k_i l_i}} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1). hkl indicate the Miller indices, I is the Bragg reflection intensity, N is the number of peaks

To evaluate the crystallite quality, crystallite sizes have been determined using the Scherrer formula (Eq. (2)), which states that the crystallite size (D) is inversely proportional to the FWHM (β), with K being the shape factor (constant). For bulk materials and polycrystalline samples, this constant can be reasonably approximated as 1.[39] Using this approach, the FWHM and D have been calculated for the most intense Bragg reflections in the patterns presented in Fig. S1. The results shown in Fig. 2c indicate that the crystallite sizes are consistently around 100 nm, with very little FWHM, suggesting that peak broadening is predominantly limited by instrumental factors, regardless of the annealing or pressure conditions. Nevertheless, the largest crystallite size – indicating the sample with the highest crystalline quality –, was observed in the sample synthesized at 1.7 MPa. This observation confirms that applying pressures below 2 MPa has a generally positive effect on film crystallinity. Furthermore, a clear correlation is observed between improved crystalline orientation and enhanced grain size.

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos(\theta)} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2). λ is the X-ray wavelength and θ is the angle for each Bragg reflection

Enhancement and consistency in the crystalline quality were further corroborated by cross-sectional SEM imaging, as shown in Fig. 2d. All

the micrographs exhibit high-quality films characterized by compact, continuous, and uniform morphologies, low surface roughness, and large columnar grains extending from the substrate interface to the film surface. This microstructural arrangement suggests a potentially reduced influence of grain boundaries on carrier transport dynamics. Notably, samples synthesized under pressures of 1.7 and 2.0 MPa display highly homogeneous and densely packed, square-shaped grains, with lateral dimensions reaching up to 500 nm. It is important to emphasize that the grain size observed in SEM corresponds to the physical grains, whereas the crystallite size (D) determined by the Scherrer equation above represents the size of individual coherent diffraction domains. Hence, the discrepancy between the D values presented in Fig. 2c and the grain sizes shown in Fig. 2d is expected. Nevertheless, the fact that these measurements are of the same order of magnitude supports the conclusion of excellent crystalline quality in the films.

Nonetheless, this study reveals an unforeseen phenomenon that might have adverse consequences for device performance. Indeed, in several regions of the samples subjected to elevated pressures – including the micrographs shown in Fig. 2d –, partial delamination of the layers deposited onto the absorber (CdS and ITO) can be observed. This suggests poor adhesion at the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface, resulting in the interfacial peeling of the overlying layers. Furthermore, this weak interfacial adhesion could lead to further deterioration of the interface between the absorber and electron transport layer (CdS), potentially increasing interfacial series resistance and carrier recombination at the junction. Therefore, further investigation and confirmation of this phenomenon is necessary, together with the development of targeted strategies to improve wettability of the CdS chemical bath on high-pressure Sb_2Se_3 surfaces. Such improvements are potentially critical for enhancing interfacial quality and overall performance of the devices. [2,36,40,41].

Building upon the previous characterization, a Raman analysis was carried out on both the absorber layers and complete devices (Fig. S3a and b, respectively). The results suggest that there are no major differences in either crystallinity or vibrational modes across the different samples. Specifically, the Raman shift of the main vibrational modes at 190 cm^{-1} and 210 cm^{-1} , along with the FWHM, remain largely unchanged regardless of the applied annealing pressure. This indicates that the composition and crystallinity of Sb_2Se_3 are robust, even when subjected under high-temperature and high-pressure conditions. However, it is worth noting that Raman spectroscopy is a surface-sensitive technique with limited penetration depth. Therefore, these observations primarily reflect the surface features of Sb_2Se_3 , where no significant changes are detected by varying pressure. In contrast, XRD provides information about the bulk of the material. Together, Raman and XRD confirm that all samples exhibit excellent crystallinity quality, with minimal variations in the FWHM. However, XRD (being a non-local technique with greater probing depth) reveals a selective enhancement in the preferred orientation along c -axis.

Despite the observed improvements in crystalline quality and (00 l) orientation, the solar cell devices do not show a significant enhancement in performance; in fact, samples subjected to higher-pressure annealing even exhibit some deterioration, as evidenced by the optoelectronic parameters shown in Fig. S4. We hypothesize that the device performance remains limited by interface deficiencies, consistent with the peeling effects observed in SEM analysis, as well as previous reports on Sb_2Se_3 solar cells.[41–43] To investigate and address this issue, various surface treatment methodologies have been developed combining photochemical UV- O_3 exposure and chemical etchings. All subsequent experiments have been conducted on films exhibiting the improved crystallographic texture to ensure a consistent starting point for interface optimization.

3.2. Surface and interface engineering on high-pressure treated Sb_2Se_3 thin films

In order to address the challenges associated with interface recombination and $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ adhesion, a comprehensive study of various surface treatments has been conducted. The objective is to develop a fast, simple, and low-cost chemical treatment implemented to the Sb_2Se_3 surface following the high-pressure post-deposition treatment, thus ensuring that the photovoltaic devices are not fundamentally limited by interfacial constraints. The experiments here have been carried out on samples treated at 1.7 MPa, as our goal is to improve the device performance through a dual strategy: achieving greater control over the absorber's texture, while minimizing the limitations that emerge from the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface. The following surface treatments have been implemented:

1. UV- O_3 treatment for 5 min
2. UV- O_3 treatment for 15 min
3. UV- O_3 treatment for 15 min + KCN (2 %) etching
4. UV- O_3 treatment for 30 min
5. UV- O_3 treatment for 30 min + KCN (2 %) etching

Following the surface treatments, photovoltaic devices have been fabricated after depositing CdS and transparent conductive oxides (see “Experimental methodology”). Then, the solar cell prototypes have been characterized by current–voltage (J-V) measurements under 1-sun illumination, see the main optoelectronic parameters for each process in Fig. 3a. Most remarkably, the hypothesis of interface limitation is confirmed, as an efficiency jump from 1.5 % to over 5 % is observed between a reference sample (no surface treatment) and the 15' UV- O_3 + KCN etched film. The absorber being synthesized under identical annealing conditions, using identical substrate, thickness and device structure, attests the importance of improving the nature of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface for device optimization. Both V_{oc} and J_{sc} present significant improvement, with the fill factor achieving values around 55 %. Otherwise, ozone treatment alone does not substantially enhance the optoelectronic properties of the materials, even resulting in a significant decrease of the J_{sc} , plunging the PCE to values under 1 %. Furthermore, 30' UV- O_3 + KCN also improved the performance with respect to the reference sample, but devices present a larger statistical dispersion of values.

To elucidate the effects of UV- O_3 and KCN treatments on the surface characteristics of Sb_2Se_3 absorbers, water contact angle (WCA) measurements and SEM imaging analyses were conducted. Fig. 3b presents the WCA results alongside top-view SEM micrographs for the untreated reference sample and samples subjected to 15 min of UV- O_3 , or UV- O_3 followed by KCN treatment. The reference sample exhibited pronounced hydrophobicity, with a WCA of approximately 83.5° (complete data in Table S1). This hydrophobic nature could hinder the nucleation of CdS during the chemical bath deposition (CBD) process, which relies on aqueous chemistry. SEM analysis revealed a relatively non-uniform surface morphology, possibly influenced by the presence of secondary phases such as metallic Se. Although only minor signals attributable to metallic Se were detected by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Fig. 1a), localized surface concentrations of Se might escape detection by bulk-sensitive techniques. Following UV- O_3 treatment, the surface became highly hydrophilic, with water droplets spreading to the point their boundaries were no longer clearly discernible, indicating a very low WCA. This increase in the hydrophilicity can be attributed to the formation of oxygen-containing functional groups induced by UV- O_3 exposure.[43] Enhanced wettability could potentially promote an excessively rapid nucleation during CdS deposition, leading to incomplete film coverage. SEM images after UV- O_3 treatment show a smoother and more uniform surface morphology, without evidence of secondary phases. Subsequent KCN etching produced a surface with intermediate wettability, with a measured contact angle of 47.8° , and further modified the surface

Fig. 3. (a) Evolution of the main optoelectronic parameters for the Sb_2Se_3 solar cells fabricated after applying different surface treatments: J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF and PCE. (b) Surface modification effects on Sb_2Se_3 after different UV- O_3 and KCN treatments. SEM top-view micrographs and WCA measurements.

morphology, as noticed in the SEM micrographs. While we hypothesize that KCN may selectively etch detrimental surface phases and improve surface homogeneity, direct evidence for the removal of specific secondary phases remains inconclusive. Additionally, previous studies have shown that KCN etching leads to an overall increase of the surface potential of Sb_2Se_3 films, suggesting that changes in work function associated with different exposed facets could influence surface tension and adhesion properties.[36] The improved uniformity and modified wettability after KCN etching are likely to facilitate better CdS nucleation and more uniform deposition. Further studies, including detailed surface chemical analyses, would be necessary to definitively assess the removal of residual secondary phases and the interfacial energy changes between Sb_2Se_3 and the CdS precursor solution.

Hence, the application of UV- O_3 and KCN surface treatments leads to a substantial enhancement in device efficiency, highlighting the critical role of $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface engineering. This improvement is attributed to improved hydrophilicity and surface morphology, promoting better CdS deposition and nucleation, while preserving the crystalline quality.

To further clarify the impact of the surface treatments on the absorber, additional Raman spectroscopy measurements were performed. As shown in Fig. S5, the Raman spectra exhibit subtle variations among the different samples. In particular, comparison between the reference sample and the sample treated with 15 min of UV- O_3 shows only minor differences in crystalline properties, as indicated by the largely unchanged full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the main Sb_2Se_3 peak at 190 cm^{-1} . Similarly, the sample subjected to the combined treatment of 15 min of UV- O_3 followed by KCN etching also maintains comparable crystalline quality. No significant changes were observed in the peaks associated with CdS. However, it is worth noting that if the surface treatments primarily induce modifications near the surface, the Raman response may be mostly dominated by the bulk material, potentially limiting its sensitivity to detect subtle changes.

Additional characterization was performed using XPS and UPS analyses; the complete XPS spectra are shown in Fig. S6a. First, an XPS depth profile analysis was carried out, demonstrating a very remarkable compositional homogeneity throughout the absorber thickness, see Fig. 4a and S6b. Moreover, the depth profiles provide important insight into the nature of the interfaces. For example, Se signals are detected

deeper within the sample compared to Sb, which intensity decreases abruptly. Additionally, the chalcogenide signals overlap for several cycles with those of Mo (the substrate). This observation is consistent with the well-known formation of a MoSe_2 interfacial layer at the $\text{Mo}/\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3$ interface. Indeed, the presence of the MoSe_2 layer is considered beneficial, as previous studies have demonstrated its role as a hole selective filter, facilitating hole extraction from the back contact and enhancing electron diffusion towards the front contact. Furthermore, its layered structure is known to promote (00 l)-preferred crystallographin orientation in the overlying Sb_2Se_3 films.[3,44–46] Secondly, a certain degree of Cd penetration into the absorber has been observed, indicating interdiffusion at the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface. In particular, a greater overlap between Se and Cd peaks is detected. Although further investigation is needed to fully understand the diffusion behaviour between CdS and the absorber, these findings confirm the complex nature of the interface, and support the implementation of surface treatments as a strategy to enhance device performance.[47] Finally, XPS atomic concentration analysis reveals a slightly Se-rich composition (around 65 at.% and 35 at.% Sb), consistent with the expected outcome of a post-deposition treatment under Se atmosphere (see Fig. 4a).

UPS was used to determine the work function (WF) and ionization energy (IE), which corresponds to the energy difference between the vacuum level and the valence band maximum (VBM) – see Fig. S7 for complete WF and VB spectra. It should be noted that UPS is a powerful technique which allows measuring energies of the VBM with respect to vacuum level, but it does not provide CBM positions. In order to present the whole band structure, the CBM was estimated by combining UPS-derived VBM values with literature-reported optoelectronic bandgap measurements – $E_{g\text{absorber}} = 1.3\text{ eV}$ for the Sb_2Se_3 , and $E_{g\text{CdS}} = 2.4$. Further details on the measurement procedure are provided in the **Experimental methodology**. Using this procedure, the band structure of surface-treated (15' UV- O_3 + KCN) and untreated samples were determined, as shown in Fig. 4b. UPS measurements were performed at the $\text{Sb}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{CdS}$ interface (where $E_{g\text{CdS}}$ was considered), as well as within the bulk of the absorber, probing a few nanometers below the surface. Remarkably, the VBM and WF of the absorber remain unchanged after the UV- O_3 and KCN treatment, measured at 4.9 and 4.1 eV, respectively. In contrast, at the interface, significant variations have been detected: the VBM shifts from 5.9 eV in the untreated sample to 5.4 eV after

Fig. 4. (a) Depth profile analysis by XPS – performed on the 15' UV-O₃ + KCN treated sample. (b) Band structure of the treated (reference) and untreated samples in different depths of the sample: red bands – interface, grey bands – absorber. Determined by UPS analysis. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

treatment, while the WF increases from 3.8 to 4.1 eV. These results demonstrate that the UV-O₃ and KCN treatments selectively modify the Sb₂Se₃'s surface, impacting the interface properties without altering the bulk electronic structure.

Finally, a stability study was conducted to assess the temporal evolution of device performance over the course of one week. Fig. 5a shows the time-dependent efficiency (PCE) for both an untreated reference sample and the sample subjected to 15' UV-O₃ exposure followed by KCN etching. Apart from the surface treatments, both samples were fabricated under identical conditions, including high-pressure post-deposition annealing at 1.7 MPa. Significantly, a progressive improvement in the device performance was observed for both samples over time. The reference sample exhibits an increase in PCE from 1.5 % to 3.0 %, while the surface-treated Sb₂Se₃ device achieved a record efficiency of 5.8 % after 7 days. This time-dependent enhancement in device performance has been previously reported in Sb₂Se₃ solar cells, and is attributed to the beneficial effects of ambient air exposure due to formation of Sb₂O₃ and Se-rich Sb₂Se₃ at the back contact, reducing the barrier height at the back interface, by facilitating an improved charge extraction and suppressing carrier recombination.[48] External quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements further support these findings, demonstrating an enhanced photoresponse in the 500–800 nm range for the surface-treated device, see Fig. 5b. The observed improvement in EQE at shorter wavelengths supports our general hypothesis that Sb₂Se₃ devices are primarily limited by interface recombination. At higher photon energy (shorter wavelengths), electron-hole pairs are mainly generated near the p-n (Sb₂Se₃/CdS) junction, where they are more susceptible to recombination at the interface. In contrast, at longer wavelengths, where carriers are generated deeper within the absorber, beyond the space charge region, there is no significant difference between the two EQE curves.[38] See Fig. S8 for the complete set of

optoelectronic parameters from the stability study (J_{sc} , V_{oc} and FF).

Notably, the 5.8 % here reported constitutes the best performance obtained thus far under our specific fabrication and processing conditions, highlighting the synergistic benefits of combining high-pressure annealing – which promotes favorable (00 l)-oriented crystallographic texture and improved crystalline quality –, with targeted interface engineering through UV-O₃ and KCN etching treatments (Fig. 5c). The inset in Fig. 5c showcases a cross-sectional SEM image of the 5.8 % device, revealing uniform absorber layer thickness, homogeneous and smooth morphology, good adhesion of the CdS layer, and large grain size.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a post-deposition selenization treatment under high pressure conditions has been applied to co-evaporated Sb₂Se₃ absorbers. It has been demonstrated that this innovative process enhances the texture coefficient along [00 l]-crystallographic direction of Sb₂Se₃ films grown on Mo, representing a new strategy for selective control of crystalline orientation in quasi-1D chalcogenides. The promoted growth parallel to the *c*-axis is particularly beneficial, as carrier transport is favored along this direction. Additionally, the treated samples exhibit high crystalline quality with crystallite sizes exceeding 100 nm. However, the improvement in crystallographic properties does not directly translate to enhanced optoelectronic performance. To further improve photovoltaic performance, various surface treatments were investigated, leading to significant efficiency gains. Power conversion efficiencies of up to 5.8 % were achieved in samples treated with UV-O₃ followed by KCN etching. These results demonstrate that the Sb₂Se₃/CdS interface constitutes a limiting element in device performance, and that specific, optimized surface treatments can unlock the material's full

Fig. 5. (a) PCE of reference and surface-treated Sb₂Se₃-based devices after 4 and 7 days from fabrication. (b) EQE of the reference and surface-treated samples (7 days after fabrication). (c) JV curve under illumination of an optimized device with 5.8 % PCE. Inset presents a cross-section SEM image of the same device.

potential. The nature of the interfaces was investigated through contact angle measurements, XPS and UPS, confirming that the effects of the treatments are localized at the interface rather than in the bulk of the absorber. In summary, this work introduces new high-pressure methodologies for the development of polycrystalline Sb_2Se_3 layers with preferred [00 l]-orientation, highlighting the necessity of interface engineering to achieve higher device efficiencies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maykel Jiménez-Guerra: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ivan Caño:** Writing – review & editing. **Alex Jiménez-Arguijo:** Writing – review & editing. **Alejandro Navarro-Güell:** Methodology. **Axel Gon-Medaille:** Investigation. **Lorenzo Calvo-Barrío:** Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Elaine Armelin:** Resources. **Ahmed H.M. Mohammed-Sadhakthullah:** Resources. **Marcel Placidi:** Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Yudania Sánchez:** Validation, Supervision, Resources. **Joaquim Puigdollers:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Edgardo Saucedo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2025.113670>.

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